

Correction

Correction: Education and WHO recommendations for fruit and vegetable intake are associated with better cognitive function in a disadvantaged Brazilian elderly population: a population-based cross-sectional study.

The PLOS ONE Staff

There is an error in the funding statement for this article. Please refer to the correct funding statement below:

This study was funded by Wellcome Trust, U.K. (GR066133MA); MS and PRM were partly funded by CNPq-Brazil. Maria Pastor-Valero was a visiting lecturer at the Preventive Medicine Department, Faculty of Medicine, São Paulo University funded by Ministerio da Educação, Brasil, programa CAPES/professor visitante do exterior, processo BEX 13827/12-0. The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

In addition, there is an error in the co-author Simon Almeida da Silva's first name. The correct name for this co-author is Simone Almeida da Silva.

Reference

1. Pastor-Valero M, Furlan-Viebig R, Menezes PR, da Silva SA, Vallada H, et al. (2014) Education and WHO Recommendations for Fruit and Vegetable Intake Are Associated with Better Cognitive Function in a Disadvantaged Brazilian Elderly Population: A Population-Based Cross-Sectional Study. PLoS ONE 9(4): e94042. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0094042

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